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Rye Broth Recipe

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We use this protocol and it's working

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Abstract

This method describes the systematic preparation of a Rye-Based Broth for use in microbiological cultures. The broth consists of rye flour, sucrose, and, optionally, B-sitosterol dissolved in dichloromethane. The method involves the careful mixing of ingredients, filtration, and handling of dichloromethane (optional), followed by autoclaving to sterilize the broth.

Troubleshooting

Preparation of Rye-Based Broth

- 1 In a 1.5-liter beaker or jug, combine 60 g of rye flour and 20 g of sucrose with 500 ml of water.
- 2 Mix the contents thoroughly.
- 3 Add 500 ml of boiling water to the mixture. Avoid boiling the solution, as starch may cause viscosity.
- 4 Stir the mixture occasionally for the next 30 minutes to keep the flour in suspension. If using a magnetic stirrer, employ gentle stirring to prevent excessive foaming.

Filtration

- 5 Filter the solution using a fine sieve, avoiding the use of filter paper.
- 6 Optionally, for a clear broth, transfer the solution into a 1-liter measuring cylinder and allow it to settle for a few hours to remove rye flour grit.

Incorporation of B-sitosterol (Optional)

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Dissolve the B-sitosterol in a small volume of dichloromethane, ensuring complete dissolution.

Note

Handle dichloromethane with glassware, avoiding plasticware.
Use a glass pasteur pipette for transferring the dichloromethane solution.

- 8 Rapidly add the dissolved B-sitosterol to the rye broth, as dichloromethane evaporates quickly.

- 9 Employ a magnetic stirrer to gently stir the mixture, ensuring homogeneity

Autoclaving

- 10 Due to the tendency of the rye broth to overflow in the autoclave, fill the Schott bottle no more than half full.

Note

Place the Schott bottle inside a metal container to contain potential overflows.